

REVIEWS

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Review of thermal runaway risks in Na-ion and Li-ion batteries: safety improvement suggestions for Na-ion batteries

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Abstract

As the demand for safer and more sustainable energy storage solutions for renewable energy sources grows, sodium-ion batteries (SIBs) emerge as a promising alternative to lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) due to their lower cost and resource abundance. However, thermal runaway (TR) hazards remain a major challenge for both battery technologies, affecting their safety, reliability, and commercialization potential. This review provides a comprehensive comparison of thermal runaway risks in SIBs and LIBs, analyzing especially the SIB's thermal stability, failure mechanisms, and safety characteristics. The discussion covers key factors influencing thermal hazards, including cathode and anode materials, electrolyte decomposition, gas evolution, separator integrity, and heat generation behaviors. Recent advancements in electrode design, electrolyte formulations, thermal management strategies, and next-generation materials are also reviewed, highlighting ongoing efforts to mitigate safety risks in SIBs. Despite notable improvements in the thermal stability of SIBs, challenges remain in achieving the same level of safety performance as commercial LIBs. By summarizing current research progress and identifying critical areas for future innovation, this review aims to guide the development of safer, thermally stable, and commercially viable sodium-ion batteries to meet the growing needs of renewable energy sources.

Keywords: Thermal Runaway, Sodium-Ion Batteries (SIBs), Safety, Thermal Stability, Next-Generation Batteries

Introduction

As the world transitions toward renewable energy and sustainable power solutions, the need for efficient and reliable energy storage systems has never been greater. Batteries play a crucial role in integrating solar, wind, and other intermittent renewable energy sources into modern power grids, ensuring a stable and continuous supply of power.

Among various energy storage technologies, lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) have become the dominant choice due to their high energy density, long cycle life, and efficiency [7, 12, 13]. However, the rapid expansion of LIB production has raised concerns over lithium resource scarcity, rising costs, and safety risks, particularly thermal runaway incidents.

These challenges have fueled the search for alternative energy storage solutions that are cost-effective, safe, and more sustainable in the long run [7, 14–16].

Sodium-ion batteries (SIBs) have gained significant attention as a viable alternative to lithium-ion batteries, primarily due to the widespread availability and lower cost of sodium [1, 17, 18]. Unlike lithium, which is concentrated in specific regions such as South America, sodium is abundant and more evenly distributed worldwide, making it a strategically advantageous resource for energy storage technologies. Additionally, since sodium and lithium share similar chemical properties, SIBs can be produced using existing LIB manufacturing infrastructure, reducing the need for entirely new production facilities and lowering overall costs [7, 19–21]. Another key advantage of SIBs is their enhanced low-temperature performance, as sodium ions exhibit higher ionic conductivity and improved diffusion properties compared to lithium ions in colder environments [7, 22–24]. This makes SIBs particularly well-suited for energy storage applications in regions with extreme temperatures. Given these benefits, SIBs are increasingly considered for large-scale stationary energy storage, where cost-efficiency, sustainability, and adaptability to different environmental conditions are more critical than achieving the highest possible energy density.

While SIBs offer a promising alternative to LIBs in terms of resource availability and cost-effectiveness (assuming large scale production and supply chain issues are sorted), safety remains a critical consideration in their large-scale deployment. One of the most significant concerns in rechargeable batteries is thermal safety, particularly the risk of thermal runaway (TR), a self-propagating, uncontrollable temperature increase that can lead to catastrophic battery failure [2, 6, 13, 26]. Thermal runaway is primarily triggered by overheating, internal short circuits, mechanical damage, or overcharging, all of which can initiate exothermic reactions within the battery [27–31]. These reactions cause electrolyte decomposition, leading to the rapid generation of flammable and toxic gases such as H_2 , CO, and organic volatiles [31, 32]. In LIBs, this phenomenon has been extensively studied, with well-documented cases of fires and explosions, underscoring the importance of rigorous thermal management strategies [32–34].

As research into SIB safety advances, key differences between LIB and SIB thermal behavior have begun to emerge. Studies indicate that SIB cathodes, particularly layered oxide materials, exhibit lower thermal stability than their lithium-based counterparts. Computed tomography and gas emission analysis has revealed that while SIBs undergo structural degradation similar to LIBs during TR, the absence of flames in some SIB chemistries could indicate a potential safety advantage. Additionally, certain Na-ion electrolytes appear to react less violently under thermal stress, further distinguishing SIBs from LIBs in terms of fire and explosion hazards.

Despite these findings, thermal runaway in sodium-ion batteries remains an under-explored area compared to LIBs. While LIB safety has been extensively researched, with strategies such as thermal management systems, modified electrolytes, and safety vent designs, similar large-scale safety assessments are still needed for SIBs. Given the increasing commercialization of SIBs, future research must focus on:

- Assessing TR tolerance and gas emission behavior under different conditions.
- Developing advanced thermal management strategies specific to Na-ion chemistry.

- Investigating new electrode materials that enhance thermal stability.
- Performing large-scale safety evaluations under real-world conditions.

By addressing these gaps, sodium-ion technology can not only provide a cost-effective and sustainable energy storage solution but also ensure high safety standards comparable to or exceeding those of LIBs. This paper explores the thermal runaway (TR) behavior of sodium-ion batteries (SIBs), comparing it to lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) to assess safety challenges and potential advantages. We discuss the mechanisms of TR, key differences in thermal stability between SIBs and LIBs, and recent advancements in experimental analysis and mitigation strategies. By addressing these aspects, this review aims to provide insights into the safety considerations and future developments of SIBs for large-scale energy storage applications.

Fundamentals of thermal runaway in batteries

Mechanism of thermal runaway

- What triggers thermal runaway in LIBs and SIBs?

Thermal runaway in batteries is a self-sustaining process, where increasing temperature triggers exothermic reactions, leading to further heat generation. Common causes include internal short circuits, overcharging, mechanical damage, battery aging, manufacturing defects or external heat exposure. It progresses in stages: initial heating, self-heating, and catastrophic failure, which can result in fire or explosion [3].

Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs), due to their high energy density and flammable electrolytes, are particularly susceptible. Key indicators of thermal runaway include rapid temperature rise, swelling, venting, smoke, or unexpected voltage/current changes [4].

In the case of SIBs, the key contributors include heat generation due to cycling, electrolyte decomposition, gas evolution & venting and exothermic reactions. Cycling was shown to generate heat, as per the research by Zhen L. et al. [5], which focused on layered oxide cathodes (P2 and O3 types). These cathodes exhibit instability during cycling, leading to phase transitions, such as rock salt formation, which releases heat and increases the risk of thermal runaway (TR).

A study conducted by Tatiana K. et al. [6] found that in sodium-ion batteries (SIBs), particularly in pouch cells with $\text{Na}_2\text{V}_2\text{O}_7(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}$ cathode chemistry, thermal runaway is triggered by the decomposition of the anode and SEDC (Sodium ethylene dicarbonate) which is equivalent to SEI in LIBs, (between 100–115°C) rather than processes at the cathode (stage 1 TR). The study also observed that around 160 °C, a secondary reaction occurs with the separator melting away leading to internal short circuit (Stage 2 TR). At approximately 180 °C, self-heating (exothermic reaction) with venting is prompted by interactions between the electrolyte and sodium, corresponding to Stage 3 TR and the temperature peaking

around 500°C. To address these challenges, adding electrolyte additives and doping cathode materials (suppresses oxygen release behavior) can improve thermal stability. Like the increase in particle size (of electrode materials) and the single crystal structure, which may suppress the oxygen release behavior and prevent heat release. Besides, the addition of sodium bis(oxalato)borate (NaBOB), that is added to nonflammable solvent trimethyl phosphate (TMP), which makes it stable until 300°C with decent ionic conductivity of $5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ [75].

Heat generation and decomposition reactions

- Sources of heat in batteries

Heat generation occurs in three stages irrespective of battery type, they are electrochemical reactions (SEI decomposition and electrolyte reactions) and Joule heating due to separator melting causing internal short circuit and exothermic reactions between electrode and electrolyte materials leading to rapid temperature rise. SEI or SEDC (Na_2CO_3) decomposition occurs between the temperatures of 80–120°C, often termed as the 1st stage of thermal runaway stage before electrolyte or separator melting [35]. When the battery gets hot enough, SEI layer can break down. This breakdown exposes the electrode to the electrolyte, causing heat to build up inside the battery, kicking off the thermal runaway process.

In stage 2 where the separator melts away, the internal short circuit occurs (causing voltage drop and leading to joule heating). The separator is a porous membrane that physically separates the anode and cathode, preventing short circuits under normal conditions. However, as temperatures rise during the early stages of thermal runaway, the separator can melt. When this happens, the electrodes come into direct contact, creating an internal short circuit. This short circuit leads to Joule heating, which is the heat generated by electrical current passing through a resistance. During charge and discharge cycles, resistance to flow of current within battery components also can be called Joule or Ohmic heating [8], However, heat generation in this case is lower than a situation where separator collapse begins.

With the increase in the temperature due to self-heating from stage 1 and 2, the electrolyte reacting with cathode (sodium) will further exacerbate the self-heating process leading to stage 3. Once thermal runaway is underway, exothermic reactions between the electrode materials (anode, cathode) and the electrolyte become dominant heat sources. These reactions are highly energetic, releasing significant heat and producing flammable and hazardous gases, which further accelerate the temperature rise and contribute to potential explosions [65].

- How these processes differ in Li-ion vs. Na-ion batteries
The processes of thermal runaways in SIBs (at Least in NTM) are very similar to the LIBs. However, the onset, separator collapse venting and max temperatures widely vary and can be studied in this paper.

Besides, due to the larger Ion size, leads to slower diffusion rates, thereby heat generated due to charge and discharge cycles will be lower, making them thermally stable [25]. The next section will provide the thermal runaway temperature point comparison between the LIBs and SIBs.

Comparison of thermal stability: Na-ion vs. Li-ion batteries

- Findings from ARC (Accelerating Rate Calorimetry) studies

Yue et al. conducted a study comparing the thermal runaway hazards of SIBs and LIBs, using accelerating rate calorimetry as a baseline analysis method. For this study, 18650 SIBs with NTM (Na_xTMO_2) cathodes and LIBs with LFP (LiFePO_4) and NCM ($\text{LiNi}_{0.5}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Mn}_{0.3}\text{O}_2$) cathodes, all similar cylindrical shape with a 16 mm diameter and 65 mm length, were tested.

This study has observed and plotted the T_{onset} (self-heating temperature- where cell starts to heat itself without external heat sources) when exceeding $0.02^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, T_{open} (safety venting temperature-the point at which the internal temperature and pressure reach critical level triggering gas venting), T_{sc} (separator collapsing temperature-where the internal resistance decline at a rapid rate leading to short circuit), and T_{max} (maximum temperature during thermal runaway-representing as a peak in bell curve of fig. 1), as represented in Fig. 1. Below is a detailed description of each stage as depicted in Fig. 1.

Stage 1: initial heating to self-heating onset

In Stage 1, the battery is externally heated using the ARC's Heat-Wait-Seek mode, where the temperature increases in controlled steps. This stage continues until the battery begins to generate heat internally, marking the onset of self-heating at T_{onset} . This transition is identified when the temperature rise rate exceeds $0.02^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, indicating the start of internal chemical reactions.

Temperature Values: LFP Battery: $T_{onset} = 124.1^\circ\text{C}$

NTM Battery: $T_{onset} = 94.0^\circ\text{C}$

NCM Battery: $T_{onset} = 97.4^\circ\text{C}$

Observation:

The temperature curve in Figure 1 shows a gradual increase during this stage, with a relatively shallow slope until T_{onset} is reached. The LFP battery has the highest T_{onset} , indicating that it requires more external heating to initiate self-heating compared to the NTM and NCM batteries.

Stage 2a: self-heating to safety venting

Stage 2a begins once self-heating is detected at T_{onset} . In this adiabatic environment, temperature rises more noticeably due to internal reactions such as SEI decomposition and reactions between the anode and the electrolyte. These reactions produce gases,

Fig. 1 Temperature variation and heating rate curves of the three types of batteries [9]

increasing internal pressure until the safety valve opens at T_{open} , releasing gases and marking the end of this stage.

Temperature Values: LFP Battery: $T_{open} = 151.5^{\circ}C$

NTM Battery: $T_{open} = 149.2^{\circ}C$

NCM Battery: $T_{open} = 167.7^{\circ}C$

Observation:

The temperature curve in Figure 1 steepens during this stage as self-heating accelerates. The NCM battery reaches the highest T_{open} , suggesting it can sustain higher

internal pressure before venting, while the NTM and LFP batteries vent at slightly lower temperatures.

Stage 2b: Safety Venting to Separator Collapse

After the safety valve opens at T_{open} , Stage 2b involves a continued temperature increase as internal reactions intensify. The release of gases does not halt heat generation. The battery approaches a critical point where the separator collapses at T_{sc} when temperature rise rate exceeds $60^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, leading to an internal short circuit and significantly accelerating thermal runaway.

Temperature Values: LFP Battery: $T_{sc} = 279.7^{\circ}\text{C}$

NTM Battery: $T_{sc} = 271.1^{\circ}\text{C}$

NCM Battery: $T_{sc} = 231.7^{\circ}\text{C}$

Observation:

Figure 1 shows a more rapid temperature rise in this stage, reflecting escalating internal reactions. The NCM battery's separator collapses at a lower temperature than the others, indicating earlier vulnerability to short-circuiting, while the LFP and NTM batteries withstand higher temperatures before this point.

Stage 3: Separator Collapse to Maximum Temperature

Stage 3 starts after the separator collapses at T_{sc} , leading to a rapid and uncontrollable temperature increase caused by internal short circuits and intense exothermic reactions. This stage peaks at T_{max} , the maximum temperature reached during thermal runaway.

Temperature Values: LFP Battery: $T_{max} = 421.0^{\circ}\text{C}$

NTM Battery: $T_{max} = 511.7^{\circ}\text{C}$

NCM Battery: $T_{max} = 748.6^{\circ}\text{C}$

Observation:

Figure 1 reveals a sharp, near-vertical temperature rise during this stage, especially for the NCM battery, which reaches the highest T_{max} . The LFP battery exhibits the lowest peak temperature, indicating less severe runaway behavior, while the NTM battery lies between the two extremes.

These temperatures were subsequently used to derive kinetic parameters, such as the pre-exponential factor (A) and activation energy (E_a), for the three types of batteries [9].

The pre-exponential factor (A) is represented as a constant in the Arrhenius equation, which describes the temperature dependence of the battery's reaction rate. The reaction rate is more significantly affected by " A ". On the other hand, the Activation Energy (E_a) is defined as the minimum amount of energy necessary for a chemical reaction in the batteries. A higher E_a can indicate slowdown in chemical reaction rate leading to decrease in charge and discharge capacities (determined by electrode materials, electrolyte, SEI, operational conditions and so on).

$$\ln\left(\frac{dT}{dt}\right) = \ln(\Delta T_{ad} \cdot A) - \frac{E_a}{R \cdot T} \quad \text{Arrhenius Equation} \quad (1)$$

Where A is the frequency factor, E_a is the activation energy, R is the gas constant, and ΔT_{ad} is the adiabatic temperature rise, i.e., the difference between T_{max} and T_{onset} . Solving this equation provides the A and E_a values of the corresponding NTM, LFP and NCM cells.

Finally, W is the TNT (Trinitrotoluene) equivalent weight in grams. $SADT$ is another variable that is defined as the temperature at which the system heat release rate is higher than the rate of heat dissipation, resulting in temperature continuing to rise until triggering the thermal runaway.

$$Q_{total} = mc\Delta T_{ad} \quad (2)$$

$$W = \eta \cdot \frac{Q_{total}}{H_{TNT}^{\frac{1}{3}}} \quad (3)$$

$$SADT = T_{NR} - \frac{R \cdot T_{NR}^2}{E_a} \quad (4)$$

Where Q_{total} is the Total TR heat production, m mass of the battery material (grams), c is the specific heat of the battery material, η is the equivalent quality coefficient, H_{TNT} (heat of detonation of TNT explosives, and its typical value is 4.437 kJ/g), T_{NR} is critical non-return temperature point.

From Figure 2 below, the thermal hazards follow the order: NCM battery > NTM battery > LFP battery. The factors T_{max} , r_{max} and W are crucial in this case, as they are external to the battery cells and directly influence safety in the event of thermal runaway.

A subsequent study on prismatic cells confirmed that NTM cells show thermal stability and hazard levels comparable to LFP cells, aligning with prior findings on cylindrical cells. Conversely, commercially available NCM523 cells displayed the lowest thermal stability and highest hazard level. NTM cells also exhibited the highest temperatures for venting and thermal runaway, providing ample time for response before a battery fire becomes unmanageable [10].

On a 4-level hazard scale, where Level 1 denotes an extreme hazard and Level 4 a mild hazard, LFP cells, with the lowest thermal risk, are rated at Levels 3 and 4. NTM cells are on the cusp of Level 2, while NCM523 is categorized as Level 1, reflecting severe hazard conditions.

The hazard levels are determined by a variable called T_{score} , which is defined as follows:

$$T_{Onset-Score} = \frac{T_{Onset}}{T_{Onset-m}} \quad (5)$$

$$T_{tr-Score} = \frac{T_{tr}}{T_{tr-m}} \quad (6)$$

Fig. 2 Comparative assessment of thermal hazards of SIB and LIBs [9]

$$T_{max-Score} = \frac{T_{max}}{T_{max-m}} \tag{7}$$

$$T_{Score} = \frac{T_{Onset-Score} + T_{tr-Score} + T_{max-Score}}{3} \tag{8}$$

Where T_{onset} is onset temperature of self-heating (0.02°C/min), T_{tr} refers to trigger temperature of thermal runaway (>1°C/min), T_{max} is the maximum temperature during thermal runaway. Finally, $T_{onset-m}$, T_{tr-m} , T_{max-m} are medians of T_{onset} , T_{tr} , T_{max} respectively. The smaller the T_{score} , the more severe the thermal hazard. Figure 3 below illustrates the severity of thermal hazards across four levels [10].

These studies reveal that battery chemistry significantly influences thermal safety. NCM poses the greatest danger, while LFP offers the best stability, with NTM providing a middle ground. These insights are crucial for understanding battery safety in various applications.

Electrochemical and Material Perspectives on Thermal Runaway

Electrode Materials and Their Influence on Thermal Stability

Cathode materials (NMC, LFP, $Na_3V_2(PO_4)_2F$, layered oxides)

The thermal and structural stability of battery cathodes is critical for performance and durability, but achieving an optimal balance in Transition Metal (TM) cathodes requires

Fig. 3 The bubble chart shows the correlation between energy density, cell type and T_{score} , where larger bubbles represent larger T_{score} , the color of bubble indicates the different cell type, and the arrows indicate the data in this work [10]

tradeoffs (decomposes at temperatures around 200°C). According to Ren J. et al., the performance and stability of NMC cathodes depend on the proportions of Ni, Mn, and Co. For instance, Co minimizes cation mixing, enhances cathode structural stability, and boosts electronic conductivity, but its high cost makes pristine Co impractical for cathode use. Ni offers a cost-effective alternative, maintaining specific capacity due to lower mining and extraction costs, but it compromises cathode structural stability. Mn, significantly cheaper than Ni and Co, provides thermal stability but introduces a spinel phase that disrupts the material's layered structure [58]. Thus, a carefully balanced combination of TMs can yield optimal results with minimal drawbacks. NMC chemistries have shown thermal runaway onset temperatures ranging from 160 to 1800 °C, depending on the specific NMC composition with energy density tradeoffs.

LFP (LiFePO₄) in its de-lithiated FePO₄ form exhibits remarkable chemical stability, remaining stable even at 200 °C in air (start to decompose between 300–400°C), thus fulfilling the safety criteria for cathode materials in power batteries. With only a small fraction of Li⁺ (6.81%) in LiFePO₄, its structural stability remains comparable to FePO₄, positioning it as one of the most thermally stable cathodes [58].

Sodium cathode chemistry significantly influences thermal stability in Na_xTMO₂. Multi-element compositions, like Na_xNi₁₃Co₁₃Mn₁₃O₂, enhance stability via

synergistic TM interactions compared single TM composition. Triple-phase (P2/O3/O1) structures delay P2-to-spinel transitions to 249 °C, outperforming binary (220°C) and single-phase (176°C) variants. NaPO₃-coated Na₂₃Ni₁₃Mn₂₃O₂ delays oxygen evolution to 480 °C (vs. 380 °C uncoated), improving capacity retention to 75% after 300 cycles. Carbon-coated NaCrO₂ maintains a hexagonal P3 phase to 320 °C (vs. 270 °C bare). Quenching eliminates TM vacancies, stabilizing O3-type NaNi_{0.4}Mn_{0.4}Co_{0.2}O₂. Organic electrolytes lower stability, necessitating robust designs to mitigate thermal runaway risks [59].

Polyanionic compounds, such as phosphates (e.g., LiFePO₄ for LIBs, Na₃V₂(PO₄)₃ for SIBs), sulfates, and other frameworks, are noted for their robust structural frameworks. These frameworks contribute significantly to their high thermal stability (decomposing temperatures are between 300–400°C) and electrochemical stability, making them safer compared to layered oxide cathodes. The presence of larger anionic groups (e.g., PO₄³⁻, SO₄²⁻) in polyanionic compounds forms a stable lattice that resists structural collapse during charge-discharge cycles, enhancing thermal safety. Polyanionic compounds are highlighted for their excellent thermal safety, which is attributed to the strong covalent bonds within the polyanionic groups (e.g., P-O bonds in phosphates). These bonds stabilize the structure against thermal runaway, reducing risks of combustion or explosion even under extreme conditions like short circuits or overcharging. They (e.g., Na₃V₂(PO₄)₂F₃, Na₂Fe₂(SO₄)₃) also demonstrate excellent cycle performance and high safety, partly due to their ability to maintain structural integrity at elevated temperatures [58].

Finally, Phosphate-based cathodes (LFP and Na₃V₂(PO₄)₂F) offer superior thermal stability compared to layered oxides (with doping), including NMC and LiCoO₂. LFP's olivine structure and Na₃V₂(PO₄)₂F's fluorinated NASICON (sodium super ion conductors) framework provide strong chemical bonds that resist decomposition, making them safer for battery applications. NMC and other layered oxides, while offering higher energy densities, are limited by lower thermal stability due to oxygen release and phase transitions. These characteristics make LFP and Na₃V₂(PO₄)₂F preferable for safety-critical applications, while NMC and layered oxides (energy density for Layered oxide is comparatively higher in the category of SIBs) are better suited for high-energy-density needs with proper thermal management [72–74].

Anode Materials (Hard Carbon, Graphite, Na Metal Anodes)

The sodium-ion anode material, hard carbon, exhibits lower thermal stability compared to the lithium-ion anode, graphite. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) reveals two exothermic peaks for sodiated hard carbon at ~190°C and ~270°C, with a total thermal effect of 610 J/g, approximately 1.5 times higher than graphite's 449 J/g at 297°C. The lower onset temperature (151.3°C) and higher thermal effect stem from the higher reactivity of the sodium-containing solid-electrolyte interface (SEI) compared to lithium-based SEI. The first peak is linked to SEI decomposition followed by reaction with the PVDF binder, while the second relates to the anode material itself. Unlike graphite's sharp peak, hard carbon's decomposition is stretched across a broader temperature range, potentially allowing more time for fire prevention systems to mitigate thermal runaway. However, the higher thermal effect indicates greater energy release, posing safety challenges. Ruslan et. al. suggests that using alternative electrolytes, beyond the

standard 1M NaPF₆ in ethylene carbonate/propylene carbonate, could enhance SEI stability, thereby improving the thermal safety of hard carbon anodes for sodium-ion batteries [61]. The incorporation of hard carbon anode materials, as noted by Tawalbeh et al., also supports stable electrochemical performance, indirectly contributing to thermal stability by minimizing side reactions [62].

Graphite, a common anode material in lithium-ion batteries, faces challenges in SIBs due to its limited ability to store sodium ions. This can lead to safety concerns, as the use of flammable non-aqueous electrolytes increases the risk of fires or explosions during thermal runaway. Additionally, sodium plating during fast charging can cause short circuits, potentially escalating into thermal issues. Modified graphite, such as expanded graphite, improves performance but lacks detailed thermal stability data. The solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) on graphite decomposes below 100 °C, intensifying between 100–150°C, releasing heat and forming compounds like Na₂CO₃ and Na₂O, contributing to thermal instability [66].

Sodium metal anodes are highly reactive, particularly with moisture, which can cause serious burns or fires that are difficult to extinguish. Dendrite formation during cycling can lead to short circuits, increasing the risk of thermal runaway. Strategies like artificial solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) layers help mitigate these risks, but the high reactivity of sodium metal remains a significant safety challenge, especially during battery processing or disassembly [67].

Anode Structural Changes in High-Temperature Conditions

The structural changes in graphite anodes for sodium-ion batteries significantly influence their thermal stability. Sodium ions, due to their larger radius compared to lithium ions, face challenges in intercalating into graphite's layered structure, leading to modifications like expanded interlayer spacing and co-intercalation with solvents. These alterations, which are noted in the research conducted by Zhan F. et al., can affect the thermal stability of the anode. For instance, co-intercalation phenomena, such as sodium-solvent complexes, may destabilize the graphite structure, increasing the risk of thermal runaway under high temperatures due to electrolyte decomposition or structural exfoliation [60]. Surface modifications, like coatings (ZIF-8 coating), enhance the solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) stability, reducing thermal degradation by preventing continuous electrolyte breakdown. Structural modifications, such as creating porous or disordered structures, improve sodium-ion diffusion but may compromise thermal stability if defects weaken the graphite lattice. Optimized electrolytes, like ether-based systems, promote stable SEI formation, enhancing thermal stability by minimizing reactive interfaces. Overall, while these modifications improve sodium storage, they must balance structural integrity to ensure thermal stability, critical for safe battery operation.

Role of Electrolytes in Thermal Safety

How Electrolyte Composition Affects Thermal Stability

The composition of sodium-ion battery (SIB) electrolytes significantly influences their thermal stability, a critical factor for safety. The review by Tawalbeh et al. highlights that pure sodium salts exhibit superior thermal stability compared to lithium salts. Accelerating rate calorimetry (ARC) experiments demonstrate that SIBs reach a maximum temperature of 312.4°C during thermal runaway, lower than lithium-ion batteries (LIBs),

indicating enhanced thermal stability. This is attributed to the inherent properties of sodium salts, which are less prone to decomposition at high temperatures. Additionally, the use of nanostructured electrolytes, such as gel polymer electrolytes, further improves thermal stability by reducing flammability and enhancing mechanical integrity. These electrolytes mitigate risks associated with thermal runaway by maintaining structural stability under elevated temperatures. Overall, optimizing electrolyte composition with stable sodium salts and nanostructured materials is key to enhancing the thermal safety of SIBs, making them a safer alternative for large-scale energy storage applications [62].

Flame-Retardant and Gel-Polymer Electrolytes

The flame-retardant gel electrolyte (FRGE) in sodium-ion batteries, composed of fully fluorinated electrolytes (FEC, FEMC), high-concentration phosphate ester (TFEP), and crosslinked gel components (DVP, PETEA), significantly enhances thermal stability in layered oxide cathode cells (especially NCFM-Nickel-Cobalt-Fluoride-Manganese). The FRGE's phosphorus-rich composition, particularly from TFEP, contributes to inherent flame retardancy, as evidenced by the GF/FRGE separator showing no change post-ignition, unlike the FFT (fluorinated electrolyte mixed with TFEP) electrolyte, which extinguishes in 10 seconds with diaphragm damage. Thermogravimetric (TG) analysis indicates superior high-temperature resistance in FRGE, attributed to its three-dimensional gel skeleton, which improves liquid retention and structural integrity. The cross-linking agent PETEA enhances this stability, facilitating ion conduction while maintaining a robust framework. Additionally, the formation of fluorine-rich compounds at the interface, due to fluorinated solvents, boosts oxidation stability from 4.0V in liquid electrolytes to nearly 5.0 V in FRGE. The FRGE electrode achieves self-extinguishing in under 0.1 seconds, compared to 6 seconds for the liquid electrolyte (LE) electrode, underscoring its superior thermal safety. This comprehensive design mitigates thermal runaway risks, ensuring enhanced safety for sodium-ion battery applications [63].

Ionic liquids as electrolytes in SIBs

A study was conducted on Ionic liquids as electrolytes in SIBs to improve thermal and electrochemical stability with negligible vapor pressure compared to organic electrolytes. These ionic liquids are a composition of large asymmetrical cations and anions. Some of the ionic liquids are Ammonium (NR_4^+), Phosphonium (PR_4^+), Sulfonium ($[\text{R}_3\text{S}]^+$ ("R" is organic substituent), Hydrogen sulphate (HSO_4^-), Dihydrogen phosphate ($[\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4]^-$) and so on [11].

In this study, a comparison was made between the Polycarbonate (organic electrolyte), and N-propyl-N-methyl Pyrrolidinium tri (fluoro-sulfonyl) imide (Pyr13FSI) (Ionic electrolyte). The difference is Polycarbonate tends to explode at 1500 C, however Pyr13FSI remained inert till 3000C. The reason behind this disparity is that high coulombic attraction (attraction between oppositely charged particles) in ionic liquids which require higher energy to break as compared to organic carbonates. Pyr13FSI in some studies also showed cycling stability with coulomb efficiency of 99.2% even after 200 cycles at 600C.

On the other hand, imidazolium-based ionic liquid electrolytes (EMImFSI) despite being ionic electrolytes similar to Pyr₁₃FSI, they tend to have low cyclic life stability, (Failure at 600 C after 60 cycles) due to non-uniform SEI layer formation and cathodic instabilities. The following figure 4 illustrates this behavior.

Fig. 4 cycle stability and coulombic efficiency of polycarbonate, EMIMFSI and Pyr14 FSI after 200 cycles, Pyr13FSI at 99.2% efficiency [11]

Impact of Solid-Electrolyte Interphase (SEI) Stability

Differences in SEI Formation Between Na-ion and Li-ion

In SIBs, the SEI primarily forms on the hard carbon (HC) anode and includes sodium ethylene dicarbonate (SEDC), which decomposes between 100–130°C, contributing to initial self-heating around 145°C. This decomposition exposes the anode, triggering secondary reactions with the electrolyte that release significant heat. In contrast, LIBs typically form a more stable SEI on graphite anodes, which decomposes at slightly higher temperatures and is less prone to extensive secondary reactions. Tatiana K. et al., notes that the gas composition post-thermal runaway in SIBs, driven by electrolyte, binder, and SEI decomposition, mirrors that of LIBs, suggesting similarities in SEI chemical components. However, the lower thermal stability of SIB SEI, coupled with the presence of sodium metal clusters in HC (Hard Carbon) micropores, intensifies self-heating compared to LIBs. These differences underscore the need for tailored electrolyte and anode designs to enhance SIB safety and stability [6].

How SEI Decomposition Influences TR Risks

The decomposition of the solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) on the HC anode in sodium-ion batteries (SIBs) significantly influences thermal runaway (TR) risks, as detailed in the study. The SEI, formed from solvent and electrolyte salt decomposition, begins to break down around 97.93°C, as observed in differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and adiabatic accelerating rate calorimeter (ARC) tests. This early decomposition, marked by the onset temperature (T_{onset}), compromises the anode's protective layer, exposing sodium metal and intensifying exothermic reactions with the electrolyte. These reactions generate flammable gases like CO, CH₄, and C₂H₄, increasing internal pressure and heat, which can trigger TR. In-situ X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) reveals

SEI degradation into compounds like Na_2CO_3 and Na_2O , further destabilizing the anode. Teng et.al. highlights that SEI instability, particularly at higher states of charge (SOC), lowers the decomposition temperature, accelerating heat and gas production in layered oxide (NFM). This contributes to a chain reaction, escalating battery temperature to a maximum of 403.6°C during TR, underscoring the critical role of SEI stability in mitigating SIB thermal risks. Unfortunately, studies in polyanion, Prussian white and alluaudite cathode material batteries do not have enough information to refer [64].

Experimental Methods and Modeling Approaches for TR Analysis

Experimental Techniques for Studying Thermal Runaway

Accelerating Rate Calorimetry (ARC)

ARC is a technique that measures the specimen's (component under testing) temperature and pressure change when heated over time [36] in adiabatic conditions (minimal heat loss conditions). This method is critical for assessing the thermal stability and potential for thermal runaway reactions in battery systems, particularly in Li-ion and Sodium-ion batteries. In Li-ion batteries, ARC evaluates the thermal behavior of cathode materials, electrolytes, and full cells, identifying critical parameters like Time to Maximum Rate (TMR), Adiabatic Decomposition Temperature (ADT₂₄), Temperature of No Return (TNR), and Self-Accelerating Decomposition Temperature (SADT). These metrics help predict exothermic decomposition, gas generation, and runaway risks under abuse conditions, such as overcharging or high temperatures. For Sodium-ion batteries, ARC is equally vital, though their different chemistries, such as hard carbon anodes and layered oxide cathodes, exhibit unique thermal profiles. ARC data aids in comparing the thermal stability of Sodium-ion cells to Li-ion, revealing safer operating windows or vulnerabilities. By simulating real-world thermal abuse scenarios, ARC guides the design of safer battery compositions, informs thermal management systems, and ensures compliance with safety standards for both technologies. The following figure 5 will explain the arrangement:

Thermal gas analysis (TGA, DSC)

Thermal gas analysis encompasses techniques that evaluate the thermal behavior and composition of materials by monitoring weight changes and evolving gases as a function of time and temperature (under cooling, heating, or isothermal conditions). Techniques include Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA), Evolved Gas Analysis (EGA), Differential Thermal Analysis, and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) [37], following figure 6 is an example of TGA. For lithium-ion batteries (LIBs), TGA is crucial for analyzing gas release composition, quantity, and chemical bonds during thermal runaway events, providing insights into safety and degradation mechanisms. Similarly, in sodium-ion batteries (SIBs), TGA and DSC are employed to study electrolyte stability, electrode material decomposition, and gas evolution under thermal stress. These techniques help identify thermal stability limits, phase transitions, and reaction kinetics, enabling the optimization of battery materials for enhanced safety and performance. DSC complements TGA by measuring heat flow, revealing endothermic or exothermic processes like melting, crystallization, or decomposition in both LIBs and SIBs. By combining TGA and DSC, researchers can comprehensively characterize the thermal and chemical behavior of

Fig. 5 a Schematic of ARC [36], b For cylindrical cell specimen [41]

Fig. 6 Schematic representation of TGA setup [42]

battery components, guiding the development of more robust and efficient energy storage systems.

In-situ microstructural analysis (XRD, SEM, TEM post-thermal exposure)

In-situ microstructural analysis characterizes material microstructures under mechanical, thermal, or other loads during deformation or temperature rise [38]. In lithium-ion batteries (LIBs), thermal events can elevate temperatures beyond 800 °C, significantly altering material microstructures. Small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) and X-ray diffraction (XRD) are critical for studying solid-state batteries (SIBs) and LIBs, identifying new phases and lattice structure changes during thermal exposure. SAXS provides insights into nanoscale structural evolution, complementing XRD's phase identification. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) reveals grain size, void formation, and surface precipitates indicative of thermal exposure, while Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) offers detailed imaging of these features. These techniques are vital for

understanding microstructural stability and degradation in SIBs and LIBs under extreme conditions, enabling the development of safer, more resilient battery technologies. The significance of SIBs lies in their potential for higher energy density and safety due to solid electrolytes, reducing flammability risks compared to LIBs. LIBs, widely used in portable electronics and electric vehicles, face challenges from thermal runaway, necessitating precise microstructural analysis to enhance performance and safety. Integrating SAXS, XRD, SEM, and TEM provides comprehensive insights into thermally induced changes, guiding material optimization for both battery types.

Modeling Thermal Runaway in Batteries

Finite Element Analysis (FEA) of heat dissipation

Finite Element Analysis (FEA) is a critical tool for studying heat dissipation in sodium-ion batteries (SIBs), which are promising for large-scale energy storage compared to real time testing [44]. Effective thermal management is essential to ensure SIB performance, safety, and longevity, as excessive heat can lead to thermal runaway, capacity degradation, and safety hazards [45]. FEA models simulate heat generation, transfer, and dissipation, guiding the optimization of battery design and thermal management systems (BTMS) [43].

An analytical study was performed on pouch and prismatic Na-ion cells based on existing Li-ion Models, due to external short circuit or ultra-high discharge rates. Based on this analytical model, the author (An et. al.) has evaluated the effectiveness of a thermal runaway prevention strategy based on boiling in mini-channels of water cooled mini-channel based BMS (battery management system) [46]. The governing equations are as follows:

$$Q_{exothermic} = Q_{sei} + Q_{ne} + Q_{pe} + Q_e \quad (9)$$

whereas Q_{sei} , Q_{ne} , Q_{pe} and Q_e are corresponding heat generation due to SEI decomposition, negative electrolyte reactions positive electrolyte decomposition and electrolyte decomposition as part of exothermic reaction.

$$K \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x^2} + Q_{nominal} + \beta(\theta + T_{inf}) = \rho C_p \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} = 0 \text{ at } x = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$K \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x^2} = h\theta \text{ at } x = \frac{w}{2} \quad (12)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \theta &= 0 \text{ at } t = 0 \\ \theta &= T - T_{inf} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

$$\beta = \frac{Q_{exothermic}}{\theta + T_{inf}} \quad (14)$$

here, β is a coefficient to be multiplied with absolute temperature to obtain exothermic reactions, w is the width of the cell, h is the convection heat transfer coefficient, t is the time, K is the coefficient of thermal conductivity, θ is the temperature increase (K), T_{inf} is the ambient temperature, $Q_{nominal}$ is the nominal heat generation in the cell. The following Fig. 7 is the C rate, T_{inf} vs core cell temperature rise.

Multi-scale modeling of TR propagation

The development of internal temperature estimation methods for sodium-ion batteries (SIB) and lithium-ion batteries (LIB) is critical for enhancing their safety and performance. Liu Y. et al.’s approach, combining electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) with machine learning (ML) regression models, addresses the pressing challenge of preventing thermal runaway—a major safety concern for both SIB and LIB. By accurately estimating internal battery temperatures, this method enables early detection of conditions that could lead to thermal runaway, thus improving battery reliability and longevity. For SIB, which are emerging as cost-effective and sustainable alternatives to LIB, ensuring safety is vital for widespread adoption in applications like electric vehicles and grid storage. Similarly, for LIB, widely used in consumer electronics and transportation, this technique enhances safety and optimizes performance. The process, applied to four commercial 26,700 SIB packs, involves analyzing EIS data, extracting parameters, and mapping them to temperatures via ML, offering a robust tool for real-time thermal management and risk mitigation in both battery types [47].

The first step in the above figure 8 indicates the EIS data in the nyquist plot providing various cell resistances, data then reduced and various parameters have been extracted in step 2 and 3. And these parameters are then mapped to various temperatures through machine/mechanical learning technique. And step 6 is the end outcome of estimated temperatures that can predict the thermal runaway situations.

Safety Strategies for Mitigating Thermal Runaway in Na-Ion Batteries

Cell Internal Chemistries

Thermal stability is a critical parameter for battery performance, especially in applications involving high operating temperatures or safety-critical environments. SIBs and LIBs, while sharing similar electrochemical principles, differ significantly in material choices due to the larger size and different chemical properties of sodium ions compared to lithium ions. This note explores how materials design can

Fig. 7 Core cell temperature (a) varying discharge rate (b) Different initial/ambient temperature [46]

Fig. 8 Process of model training and internal temperature estimation [47]

enhance thermal stability, comparing SIBs and LIBs across key components: cathodes, anodes, electrolytes, and separators.

Cathode Material Strategies: Cathode materials are pivotal for thermal stability, as they often contribute to thermal runaway risks under high temperatures. Research suggests that SIBs can leverage polyanionic compounds for enhanced thermal stability. For instance, $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_3$ (NVPF) is noted for its excellent conductivity and structural stability across a wide temperature range (-45°C to 55°C), with a theoretical energy density of 507 Wh kg^{-1} [68]. This is achieved through strategies like carbon coating, micro-nano structuring, and element doping, which improve thermal resilience. In contrast, LIBs often use layered oxides like LiNiMnCoO_2 (NMC) (performance starts to drop above 32°C ambient temperatures), which can be thermally unstable, especially at high states of charge. However, LiFePO_4 (LFP) in LIBs is known for higher thermal stability, with studies indicating better performance under thermal stress compared to NMC [68].

The comparison highlights that SIBs may have an advantage with polyanionic cathodes, offering higher thermal stability than many LIB cathode options, particularly NMC. Strategies like defect engineering and doping, as detailed in ScienceDirect, further enhance SIB cathode stability, making them suitable for high-temperature applications.

Anode Material Optimization: Anode materials also play a significant role in thermal stability, with volume changes and reactivity under high temperatures being key concerns. In SIBs, hard carbon is a standard choice, offering capacities up to 300 mAh/g and good thermal stability. Titanium-based anodes, such as $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$, are particularly promising, with low volume expansion ($<4\%$) and stable cycling for 200 days at -40°C without capacity degradation, indicating potential for high-temperature resilience [68], however they are expensive.

For LIBs, graphite anodes are common, providing good thermal stability but limited capacity. High-capacity materials like silicon, while promising, require additional stabilization (e.g., coatings) to mitigate thermal issues, as discussed in Section 3.1. The evidence leans toward SIB anodes, especially hard carbon and titanium-based options, offering better intrinsic thermal stability due to lower reactivity and volume changes under thermal stress. Strategies for SIB anodes include morphology engineering, heteroatom doping, and surface coating, which accelerate Na^+ intercalation and provide active adsorption sites, potentially enhancing thermal stability. These approaches contrast with LIBs, where silicon anodes often need more complex stabilization to achieve similar thermal performance.

Electrolyte Engineering: Electrolytes are a major factor in thermal stability, with flammable organic electrolytes in LIBs posing significant safety risks. In SIBs, non-flammable options like glyme-based electrolytes are highlighted for enhancing safety. For example, a non-flammable glyme-based electrolyte with sodium tetrafluoroborate as the salt is noted for improving safety, reducing thermal runaway risks. Ester-based electrolytes with fluorinated solvents, such as 1.0 M NaTFSI-FEC/FEMC/fluorobenzene (3:3:4), maintain stability at -20°C for 500 cycles, suggesting potential for high-temperature performance. Solid-state electrolytes, including ceramic-based, sulfide-based, and polymer options, are also explored for unwavering thermal stability, particularly in low-temperature conditions, which could extend to high-temperature applications.

In LIBs, flammable organic electrolytes (e.g., ethylene carbonate, dimethyl carbonate) are common, contributing to thermal runaway risks. The shift toward solid-state electrolytes in LIBs mirrors SIB strategies, but SIBs seem to have an advantage with aqueous and non-flammable options, reducing thermal risks compared to LIBs. Strategies for electrolyte design include selecting sodium salt anions, using multi-solvent components, and incorporating additives to lower viscosity and stabilize the solid electrolyte interphase (SEI). These approaches enhance thermal stability, particularly for SIBs, by reducing desolvation energy and improving interfacial compatibility.

Separator Optimization: Separators, while less discussed in the sources, are crucial for thermal stability, acting as a barrier to prevent short circuits during thermal runaway. Both SIBs and LIBs can benefit from thermally stable separators, such as ceramic-coated or composite separators with high melting points. For instance, ceramic-coated separators by incorporating barium titanate (BaTiO_3) in PVDF-HFP/poly (butyl methacrylate) (PBMA) polymers, the separator can withstand the temperatures around 500°C .

Many studies support the above claim by discussing overall safety improvements in SIBs, which could include separator design. Given SIBs' higher intrinsic material stability, they may benefit more from separators designed for higher operating temperatures, though specific data is limited. General battery literature suggests that separators like those with polyethylene or polypropylene, enhanced with ceramic coatings, are standard for both, but SIBs might leverage these more effectively due to lower flammability risks.

Thermal Management Systems

Passive cooling: **Phase change materials (PCMs)**

Many studies were conducted on the passive cooling techniques of the battery systems using Phase change materials with their latent heat of fusion properties, tending to absorb the heat during charging and discharge cycles and maintain the uniformity of battery temperature [48] [40]. The optimal melting temperature prescribed as 5–10°C above the ambient for better Battery thermal Management System (BTMS) performance. Javani et al performed the studies on the PCM and concluded that 3 mm thick PCM layer shows 10% more temperature uniformity than any other thickness, also 12 mm thickness will provide the optimal cooling effect [49] [50]. Some studies showed that charge capacities and mechanical vibrations play a crucial role in performance of BTMS. For example, Du. W. et al found that 8C charge/discharge rate tends to distribute the temperature uniformly and has better cooling effect than the lower discharge rates. Also, a vibration condition of 30 mm displacement Sine dwell at 20 Hz lowered the surface temperature by 2.28K compared to non-vibration conditions [51].

However, due to low thermal conductivities of the PCM, it is advisable to go with hybrid BTMS like double sided cold plate with water as a fluid in circulation and recommended for industrial usage as per wang et al [52].

Active cooling: **Liquid cooling and heat dissipation designs.**

Active cooling involves external sources involved in circulating the air or liquid coolant to maintain the optimal battery performance temperatures. As mentioned, passive cooling (PCM) solely not enough to maintain the temperatures, instead of cold plate or copper foam layers with cooling tubes or other designs will help to bring down temperatures much faster. For example, Yanqi et al, as shown in the following figure 9, has a battery pack consisting of twenty 18650 cylindrical cells arranged in a module with copper tubes running into and out for heat exchange [53].

In another study conducted by Wenhui et al, the cold plates carrying coolant arranged with dimensions every 5 cells as shown in the following figures 9 and 10 The importance of these prismatic cell arrangements is mainly based on the heat generated vs heat dissipated for optimal performance. Like the case of active cooling, the vibrations have reasonable impact on the performance of the cold plates there by impacting the dissipation rate [54] [39].

Safety Evaluation Standards

Current **regulations and testing protocols** for Na-ion battery safety.

Since Na-ion batteries are secondary batteries (rechargeable), many regulations are in place to make them safer. The following are the regulations based on their application

Shipping: Initially UN38.3 (DGR 3.9.2.6) specified tests need to be performed, only after a pass, these tests, the following regulation tests need to be performed [55].

- UN3551-with organic electrolyte and tested at 30%SOC (State of Charge) as per packaging instruction PI 976.
- UN3552- if batteries contained in equipment or packed with equipment, with packaging Instruction P977, P978-sections I and II.
- UN 2795 for aqueous alkali electrolytes.

Fig. 9 Geometric model of the BTMS with mini-channel cold plate (a) Schematic diagram of the BTMS (b) Mini-channel cold plate and the cross-section of channel [54]

Energy storage systems (Stationary): UL1973, these are specified to check the reliability of individual battery systems and cells under real time application parameters. UL9540A for rack level testing, especially thermal propagation tests (cell to cell propagation by nail penetration or increase in temperature with heat pad) [56].

Electric vehicles: UL2580, while this standard was initially focused on Li-ion batteries, by default due to similar road transport abuse conditions, with the aim to make the battery systems safe and reliable [57].

Future Perspectives and Challenges

Safety Concerns in Na-ion Batteries

Despite the promising thermal stability of sodium-ion batteries (SIBs) compared to lithium-ion batteries (LIBs), several safety concerns persist. The lower thermal stability of the solid-electrolyte interphase (SEI) on hard carbon anodes, which decompose at approximately 100–130 °C, poses a significant risk due to its potential to trigger early self-heating and exothermic reactions. The higher thermal effect of sodiated hard carbon (610 J/g compared to 449 J/g for graphite) indicates greater energy release during thermal runaway (TR), increasing the risk of fire or explosion. Additionally, the reactivity of sodium metal clusters in hard carbon micropores can intensify self-heating, particularly at higher states of charge (SOC). The variability in thermal runaway onset temperatures (T_{onset}) and maximum temperatures (T_{max}) across different cathode chemistries, such as layered oxides (e.g., NTM) and polyanionic compounds, complicates the design of universally safe SIBs. External factors, such as mechanical abuse, overcharging, or manufacturing defects, further exacerbate these risks, necessitating robust safety measures.

Fig. 10 Geometric model of the BTMS with mini-channel cold plate (a) Schematic diagram of the BTMS (b) Mini-channel cold plate and the cross-section of channel [56]

Next-Generation Materials That Could Enhance Thermal Stability

Advancements in electrode and electrolyte materials offer promising avenues for improving the thermal stability of SIBs. For cathodes, multi-element compositions, such as $\text{Na}_x\text{Ni}_{13}\text{Co}_{13}\text{Mn}_{13}\text{O}_2$ with triple-phase (P2/O3/O1) structures, have demonstrated delayed phase transitions (up to 249 °C), enhancing structural stability. Polyanionic compounds, like $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_3$, benefit from strong covalent bonds (e.g., P-O bonds), which resist structural collapse at elevated temperatures, making them ideal for high-safety applications. Surface coatings, such as NaPO_3 or carbon layers, can further delay oxygen evolution and improve capacity retention. For anodes, alternative materials to hard carbon, such as modified graphite with expanded interlayer spacing or nanostructured alloys, could reduce the thermal effect and enhance SEI stability. Electrolyte innovations,

such as ionic liquids (e.g., Pyr13FSI), exhibit negligible vapor pressure and remain stable up to 300 °C, significantly outperforming organic carbonates. Flame-retardant gel electrolytes (FRGE) with phosphorus-rich compositions also enhance thermal safety by reducing flammability and improving oxidation stability. These materials, combined with nanostructured designs, hold potential for next-generation SIBs with superior safety profiles.

Need for standardized safety testing for Na-ion technology

The lack of standardized safety testing protocols tailored for SIBs hinders their widespread adoption, particularly in applications like electric vehicles and large-scale energy storage. While existing standards, such as UN38.3, UL1973, and UL2580, address some safety aspects, they are primarily designed for LIBs and may not fully account for the unique thermal and electrochemical characteristics of SIBs, such as the lower SEI decomposition temperature and higher gas evolution during thermal runaway. Standardized testing should include specific metrics for T_{onset} , T_{max} , and gas composition analysis under various abuse conditions (e.g., overcharging, mechanical damage, and thermal exposure). Accelerating rate calorimetry (ARC) and thermal gas analysis (TGA/DSC) should be integrated into these protocols to quantify thermal stability and hazard levels accurately. Furthermore, harmonized global standards are needed to ensure consistency in evaluating SIB safety across different chemistries and form factors, facilitating regulatory compliance and consumer confidence.

Optimal cell design: material and structural gaps in the literature

Optimizing Cathode Compositions and Structures

The thermal stability of SIB cathodes is heavily influenced by their composition and structure, yet significant gaps remain in achieving optimal designs. Multi-element compositions like $\text{Na}_x\text{Ni}_{13}\text{Co}_{13}\text{Mn}_{13}\text{O}_2$ enhance stability through synergistic interactions of transition metals (TMs), with triple-phase (P2/O3/O1) structures delaying P2-to-spinel transitions to 249 °C, compared to 220 °C for binary and 176 °C for single-phase variants. Coatings such as NaPO_3 on $\text{Na}_{23}\text{Ni}_{13}\text{Mn}_{23}\text{O}_2$ push oxygen evolution to 480 °C (versus 380 °C uncoated), and carbon-coated NaCrO_2 maintains stability to 320 °C (versus 270 °C bare). However, there is enough literature specificity on the optimal proportions of Ni, Mn, and Co or the precise mechanisms by which these modifications enhance thermal stability. For instance, while Mn provides thermal stability, it introduces a spinel phase that disrupts layered structures, and the trade-offs in NMC compositions (thermal runaway onset at 160–180 °C) are not fully resolved. Polyanionic compounds like $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ and $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_3$ offer high thermal stability (decomposing at 300–400 °C) due to robust frameworks, but the literature doesn't provide any detailed comparisons across compositions or against layered oxides. This gap necessitates research to identify exact compositions and structural modifications that maximize thermal stability and delay TR.

Enhancing Anode Stability

Anode materials in SIBs present distinct thermal stability challenges, with hard carbon, graphite, and sodium metal each revealing specific gaps. Hard carbon, a

common SIB anode, exhibits lower thermal stability than graphite in lithium-ion batteries (LIBs), with exothermic peaks at ~ 190 °C and ~ 270 °C and a thermal effect of 610 J/g (versus 449 J/g for graphite at 297 °C). The literature suggests alternative electrolytes beyond 1 M NaPF₆ in ethylene carbonate/propylene carbonate could stabilize the SEI, but it does not specify which electrolytes or how they reduce thermal effects. For graphite anodes in SIBs, limited sodium storage capacity and sodium plating risks during fast charging heighten thermal instability, with SEI decomposition below 100 °C intensifying heat release. Modified graphite (e.g., expanded graphite) improves performance, but the literature lacks thermal stability data for these variants. These gaps highlight the need to develop electrolytes that enhance SEI stability on hard carbon and to quantify the thermal behavior of modified graphite anodes to mitigate TR risks.

Improving sodium metal anodes

Sodium metal anodes pose significant safety challenges due to their high reactivity and dendrite formation, which can lead to short circuits and TR. The literature notes that artificial SEI layers help mitigate these risks, but it provides no details on their effectiveness in preventing TR or their thermal stability under high-temperature conditions. With sodium's reactivity with moisture potentially causing fires and dendrite-induced short circuits escalating thermal issues, this gap is critical. Research is needed to design and test protective layers or strategies that reduce reactivity and dendrite growth while ensuring thermal stability, making sodium metal anodes safer for SIB applications.

Advancing electrolyte technologies

Electrolytes are pivotal to SIB thermal safety, yet gaps remain in optimizing their composition and practicality. Sodium salts show superior thermal stability compared to lithium salts, with SIBs reaching a maximum TR temperature of 312.4 °C (versus higher for LIBs), and nanostructured gel polymer electrolytes reduce flammability. However, specific thermal stability data for these electrolytes in SIBs is absent. Flame-retardant gel electrolytes (FRGE) with components like TFEP enhance flame retardancy and high-temperature resistance (self-extinguishing in < 0.1 s versus 6 s for liquid electrolytes), but scalability and cost-effectiveness are unaddressed, besides focusing on salt additives like sodium bis(oxalato)borate (NaBOB) or hexafluorophosphate (NaPF₆) to TMP (Tetramethyl phosphate) electrolyte, 10 vol% FEC (Fluoroethylene carbonate) additives to organic electrolytes. Ionic liquids like Pyr13FSI remain inert to 300 °C (versus polycarbonate exploding at 150 °C), yet optimization for SIB compatibility with electrodes and electrochemical performance is lacking. These gaps call for quantifying thermal stability across electrolyte types and developing scalable, cost-effective options that balance safety and performance.

Stabilizing the SEI

The SEI in SIBs, primarily on hard carbon anodes, is less stable than in LIBs, decomposing at 100–130 °C (versus higher temperatures in LIBs) and triggering self-heating

at ~ 145 °C. This early breakdown, driven by components like sodium ethylene dicarbonate (SEDC), exposes the anode to secondary reactions, releasing heat and flammable gases (e.g., CO, CH₄, C₂H₄) that escalate TR risks. The literature notes the need for tailored electrolyte and anode designs but offers no specific solutions. This gap underscores the urgency of developing strategies—such as electrolyte additives or anode coatings—to stabilize the SEI, preventing early decomposition and reducing TR risks in SIBs.

Thermal management strategies: system-level approaches

Thermal management strategies are crucial for maintaining optimal operating temperatures and preventing TR at the system level. These strategies include both passive and active methods to dissipate heat and monitor battery conditions. For LIBs, which have been extensively studied, several approaches are well-documented:

Cell Coolants: Liquid coolants, such as a mixture of water and glycol with a heat capacity of 3.4 kJ kg K^{-1} , are popular for their efficiency in providing uniform temperature distribution. However, they add cost and volume to the system [71].

Phase Change Materials (PCMs): Materials like paraffin wax and sodium thiosulfate pentahydrate absorb heat during their phase change, helping to reduce peak exothermic rates. For instance, a study by Dai et al., 2022, found that paraffin PCM and composite PCM reduced the peak exothermic rate from 29 kW to 15.5 kW with the addition of a flame retardant, enhancing safety [69].

Mist Cooling: This involves immersing cells in an evaporating liquid to maintain uniform temperature, though it may increase hydrogen fluoride (HF) gas production, posing additional safety concerns [71].

Battery Management Systems (BMS): BMS plays a critical role in monitoring and adapting to prevent TR. Techniques include cell balancing, which applies resistance to higher output cells to equalize charge, though it can be slow and reduce available energy over time. Thermal runaway tracks detection temperature increases using non-invasive methods and modeling for core temperature, while pressure sensors detect gas release. Mitigation strategies include triggering shutdowns, releasing inert gases, adjusting safety valves, and using protective caged structures [71].

Cell Design for Thermal Stability: Incorporating materials like Positive Temperature Coefficient (PTC) materials, which increase resistance with temperature (e.g., Ba_{0.9}Sr_{0.1}TiO₃ activates at 54 °C, poly(3-decylthiophene) decreases conductivity by three orders at 80 °C), and graphene, which reduces operating temperature by 25 °C due to high thermal conductivity, enhances thermal management. Robust casings, such as polycarbonate with 250 times the impact resistance of glass, and nanocomposite mixtures for enhanced flame resistance, also contribute to safety.

For SIBs, while specific thermal management strategies are less documented, the general principles applied to LIBs are likely relevant. The importance of Battery Thermal Management Systems (BTMS) for LIBs in EVs and hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs) to maintain optimal temperatures is well-established, with references to numerous studies highlighting their role [70].

Conclusion

Summary of key findings from comparative studies

Comparative studies between lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) and sodium-ion batteries (SIBs) highlight distinct differences in thermal runaway (TR) behavior, heat generation, and material influences on safety. Thermal runaway, a self-sustaining process triggered by internal short circuits, overcharging, mechanical damage, or external heat, progresses through initial heating, self-heating, and catastrophic failure stages in both battery types. In LIBs, high energy density and flammable electrolytes lead to rapid temperature increases, swelling, and severe outcomes like fires or explosions. For SIBs, heat generation arises from cycling-induced exothermic reactions, electrolyte decomposition, and gas evolution, particularly with layered oxide cathodes (e.g., P2 and O3 types) that undergo phase transitions, elevating TR risks.

Heat generation occurs in three stages across both systems, driven by electrochemical reactions (e.g., solid-electrolyte interphase (SEI) or sodium ethylene dicarbonate (SEDC) decomposition) and Joule heating from internal short circuits. In LIBs, SEI decomposition begins at 80–120 °C, while in SIBs, SEDC decomposes at 100–115 °C, followed by separator collapse and electrolyte reactions, with peak TR temperatures reaching approximately 500 °C in SIBs and up to 748.6 °C in LIBs with NCM cathodes.

Accelerating Rate Calorimetry (ARC) studies on 18,650 cylindrical cells provide detailed insights. SIBs with Na_xTMO_2 (NTM) cathodes show a self-heating onset (T_{onset}) at 94.0 °C, safety venting at 149.2 °C, separator collapse at 271.1 °C, and a maximum TR temperature (T_{max}) of 511.7 °C. Comparatively, LIBs with LiFePO_4 (LFP) cathodes exhibit a higher T_{onset} of 124.1 °C and a lower T_{max} of 421.0 °C, while NCM-based LIBs reach a T_{max} of 748.6 °C, indicating SIBs' thermal hazards fall between LFP and NCM LIBs.

Electrode and electrolyte materials significantly affect TR behavior. Polyanionic cathodes like $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_3$ in SIBs offer superior thermal stability due to strong covalent bonds, contrasting with layered oxides in both systems that release oxygen and undergo phase transitions. Electrolytes such as ionic liquids (e.g., Pyr13FSI) in SIBs remain stable up to 300 °C, while organic carbonates in LIBs decompose earlier, increasing TR risks.

Safety advantages and challenges of Na-ion batteries

Sodium-ion batteries (SIBs) offer notable safety advantages over lithium-ion batteries (LIBs), primarily due to their enhanced thermal stability and material properties. SIBs exhibit lower maximum TR temperatures, with ARC studies reporting a T_{max} of 312.4 °C compared to higher values in LIBs, attributed to the stability of sodium salts and the potential for non-flammable electrolytes like glyme-based systems or ionic liquids (e.g., Pyr13FSI, stable up to 300 °C). Polyanionic cathodes, such as $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_3$, provide robust structural stability, resisting decomposition at high temperatures, unlike the layered oxides prevalent in LIBs.

However, SIBs face safety challenges, particularly with the solid-electrolyte interphase (SEI) on hard carbon anodes. The SEI decomposes at 100–130 °C, earlier than in LIBs, initiating self-heating and increasing TR risks. Sodiated hard carbon exhibits a higher thermal effect (610 J/g vs. 449 J/g for graphite in LIBs), releasing more energy during TR and posing fire hazards. Sodium metal clusters in hard carbon micropores further

amplify exothermic reactions, especially at higher states of charge. Variability in TR behavior across SIB chemistries—layered oxides versus polyanionic compounds—complicates consistent safety design.

Electrolyte composition also influences safety. While ionic liquids enhance stability, their cost and non-uniform SEI formation limit adoption. Flame-retardant gel electrolytes (FRGE) improve oxidation stability and reduce flammability, but their development remains nascent. Thus, while SIBs benefit from inherent thermal advantages, SEI instability and material reactivity present ongoing challenges requiring targeted solutions.

Potential advancements in battery safety research

Future advancements in sodium-ion battery (SIB) safety research focus on next-generation materials, standardized testing, and advanced cell designs to mitigate thermal runaway (TR) risks. Multi-element cathode compositions, like $\text{Na}_x\text{Ni}_{13}\text{Co}_{13}\text{Mn}_{13}\text{O}_2$ with triple-phase structures, delay phase transitions to 249 °C, enhancing stability. Polyanionic cathodes (e.g., $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_3$) leverage strong covalent bonds for superior thermal resilience, while surface coatings (e.g., NaPO_3 , carbon) delay oxygen release and improve capacity retention. For anodes, alternatives to hard carbon, such as modified graphite or nanostructured alloys, could stabilize the SEI and reduce thermal effects. Electrolytes like ionic liquids (e.g., Pyr13FSI, stable to 300 °C) and flame-retardant gel electrolytes (FRGE) with phosphorus-rich compositions enhance thermal safety by reducing flammability.

Standardized safety testing tailored for SIBs is critical, as current protocols (e.g., UN38.3, UL1973) are LIB-centric and overlook SIB-specific risks like lower SEI decomposition temperatures. Integrating ARC and thermal gas analysis (TGA/DSC) into SIB-specific standards would quantify T_{onset} , T_{max} , and gas evolution, ensuring consistent safety assessments.

Cell design and thermal management offer further potential. Passive cooling with phase change materials (PCMs) absorb heat during cycling, while active cooling systems, like liquid-cooled plates, provide rapid heat dissipation. Battery Management Systems (BMS) with real-time monitoring and predictive models can detect TR early, enabling timely interventions. These advancements, combining material innovation and system-level strategies, promise to elevate SIB safety for large-scale applications.

Abbreviations

LIBs	Lithium-ion Batteries
SIBs	Sodium-ion Batteries
TR	Thermal Runaway
SEI	Solid Electrolyte Interphase
SEDC	Sodium Ethylene Dicarboxylate (equivalent to SEI in LIBs)
ARC	Accelerating Rate Calorimetry
LFP	Lithium Iron Phosphate (LiFePO_4 , a cathode material)
NCM	Nickel Cobalt Manganese (a cathode material, e.g., NCM523)
NTM	Sodium Transition Metal (a cathode material for SIBs)
TGA	Thermogravimetric Analysis
DSC	Differential Scanning Calorimetry
XRD	X-ray Diffraction
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
TEM	Transmission Electron Microscopy
FEA	Finite Element Analysis
BTMS	Battery Thermal Management System
PCMs	Phase Change Materials

TMR	Time to Maximum Rate
ADT	Adiabatic Decomposition Temperature
TNR	Temperature of No Return
SADT	Self-Accelerating Decomposition Temperature
NMC	Nickel Manganese Cobalt (a cathode material, similar to NCM)
TM	Transition Metal
FRGE	Flame-Retardant Gel Electrolyte
FEC	Fluorinated Ethylene Carbonate (an electrolyte component)
FEMC	Fluorinated Ethyl Methyl Carbonate (an electrolyte component)
TFEP	Tris(2,2,2-trifluoroethyl) Phosphate (a phosphate ester in FRGE)
DVP	Divinyl Phosphazene (a gel component in FRGE)
PETEA	Pentaerythritol Tetraacrylate (a cross-linking agent in FRGE)
NFM	Nickel Fluoride Manganese (a layered oxide cathode material)
EIS	Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy
ML	Machine Learning
SOC	State of Charge
XPS	X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy
Pyr13FSI	N-propyl-N-methyl Pyrrolidinium Tri(flurosulfonyl) Imide (an ionic liquid electrolyte)
EMImFSI	Imidazolium-based Ionic Liquid Electrolyte
P2, O3, O1	Types of layered oxide cathode structures
Na ₃ V ₂ (PO ₄) ₂ F	Sodium Vanadium Phosphate Fluoride (a cathode material)
Na ₂ V ₂ O ₂ (PO ₄) ₂ F	Sodium Vanadium Oxide Phosphate Fluoride (a cathode material)
Na _{0.5} CrO ₂	Sodium Chromium Oxide (a cathode material)
Na _{0.6} Cr _{0.6} Ti _{0.4} O ₂	Sodium Chromium Titanium Oxide (a cathode material)
NaNi _{1/3} Fe _{1/3} Mn _{1/3} O ₂	Sodium Nickel Iron Manganese Oxide (a cathode material)
Na _{2/3} Ni _{1/3} Mn _{2/3} O ₂	Sodium Nickel Manganese Oxide (a cathode material)
NaCrO ₂	Sodium Chromium Oxide (a cathode material)
NaPO ₃	Sodium Phosphate (a coating material)
PVDF	Polyvinylidene Fluoride (a binder material)
NaPF ₆	Sodium Hexafluorophosphate (an electrolyte salt)
ZIF-8	Zeolitic Imidazolate Framework-8 (a coating material)
HC	Hard Carbon (an anode material)
FFT	Fluorinated electrolyte mixed with TFEP
T_{onset}	Onset Temperature of Self-Heating
T_{open}	Temperature of Venting
T_{sc}	Temperature of Short Circuit
T_{max}	Maximum Temperature during Thermal Runaway
T_{tr}	Trigger Temperature of Thermal Runaway
T_{inf}	Ambient temperature
$Q_{nominal}$	Nominal heat generation in the cell
A	Pre-exponential Factor (in Arrhenius equation)
E_a	Activation Energy
R	Gas Constant
ΔT_{ad}	Adiabatic Temperature Rise
Q_{total}	Total Thermal Runaway Heat Production
TNT	Trinitrotoluene
W	TNT Equivalent Thermal Runaway Heat Generation
η	Equivalent Quality Coefficient
H_{TNT}	TNT Heat Equivalent
T_{NR}	Non-return temperature point
T_{score}	Thermal Hazard Score
θ	Temperature rise (K)
β	Temperature-dependent exothermic reaction coefficient
K	Thermal conductivity
w	Cell width and height
h	Convection heat transfer coefficient
t	Time
NCFM	Nickel Cobalt Fluoride Manganese
EGA	Evolved Gas Analysis

Acknowledgements

The author sincerely thanks Enersys Delaware Inc. for their crucial financial support, which made this research possible.

Authors' contributions

AB has extracted the information from various sources, analyzed and presented in the manuscript.

Funding

This research was fully funded by Enersys Delaware Inc. The funding, including the application fees provided by Enersys Delaware Inc enabled the acquisition of necessary resources for the study. The author expresses his gratitude for Enersys's financial support, which made this work possible.

Data availability

The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Declarations**Competing interests**

Not applicable.

Received: 24 April 2025 Accepted: 11 June 2025

Published online: 14 July 2025

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